

Clinical Profile of H. S Purpura in Children in Teaching InstitutePriyanka Sharma¹, Ravinder Gupta², Sakshi Sahni³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, ASCOMS and Hospital, Sidhra, Jammu, India²Professor & Head, Department of Paediatrics, ASCOMS and Hospital, Sidhra, Jammu, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, ASCOMS and Hospital, Sidhra, Jammu, India

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Priyanka Sharma

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: HENOCHE-Schoenlein purpura (HSP) is a multisystem disorder affecting predominantly the skin, joints, gastrointestinal tract and kidneys, although involvement of other organs can occur rarely. It is one of the most common causes of immunoglobulin A (IgA) mediated systemic small vessel vasculitis with IgA deposition in vessel walls leading to symptoms involving the skin, joints, intestines, and kidneys in children the world-over.

Methods: This hospital based descriptive study was conducted at a major tertiary care teaching hospital in North India. All children were diagnosed as HSP, according to the 2010 European League against Rheumatism criteria⁷, admitted at various wards in the Department of Paediatrics, during the period of six months from June 2021 to December 2021 were included in the study

Results: In this study, 65 patients were included. The mean age at presentation was 6.5 years (Range 2 to 12 years). There were 40 boys and 25 girls with a male preponderance (male to female ratio 1.6:1). The common presenting symptoms were purpuric rash (n=65,100%), pain abdomen (n=42,64%), and arthritis (n=28,44%), vomiting (n=16,24%), Malena (n=3,5%), genitourinary symptoms like hematuria (n=3,4%), scrotal pain (n=4,6%), oedema (n=10,15%), hypertension (n=20,30%) were seen. In the laboratory parameters An elevated ESR (n=31,48%), anaemia (n=33,50%), leucocytosis seen in 5 cases (18%), thrombocytosis in 13 (20%) patients. ASO titre of >200 was found in 10 (15%) patients. Abnormal urine analysis in 10 (15%) patients. Rheumatoid factor was positive in 17(4%) also stool for occult was positive in 12(19%) cases.

Conclusion: The clinical features of Henoch Schonlein purpura in the population were different from the previously published studies. Renal involvement was less common the occurrence of life-threatening complications in HSP is very rare

Keywords: HSP, India, Clinical Profile.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

HENOCHE-Schoenlein purpura (HSP) is a multisystem disorder affecting predominantly the skin, joints, gastrointestinal tract and kidneys, although involvement of other organs can occur rarely. It is one of the most common causes of immunoglobulin A (IgA) mediated systemic small vessel vasculitis with IgA deposition in vessel walls leading to symptoms involving the skin, joints, intestines, and kidneys in children the world-over [1-5] This autoimmune vasculitis is characterized by multi organ involvement in the form of non-thrombocytopenic palpable purpura, abdominal pain, arthritis and haematuria. The annual incidence of Henoch Schoenlein Purpura in children is around 14-20 per 1,00,000 population. [6] It usually has a self-limited course but has the potential to cause serious life-threatening complications including gastrointestinal perforation and end stage renal disease. Although the clinicopathological profile of HSP has been studied before, data from the northern part

of our country are lacking. Hence, this study was planned to describe the clinical profile of HSP in children admitted in our institute

Methods

This hospital based descriptive study was conducted at a major tertiary care teaching hospital in North India. All children were diagnosed as HSP, according to the 2010 European League against Rheumatism criteria⁷, admitted at various wards in the Department of Paediatrics, during the period of six months from June 2021 to December 2021 were included in the study. A detailed history and systemic examination were done in all the patients. The criteria include palpable purpura which is a mandatory criterion with the presence of at least one of the following features such as diffuse abdominal pain, any biopsy showing predominant IgA deposition, arthritis or arthralgia, and renal involvement in the form of haematuria and/or pro-

teinuria These children were followed up for six months to detect complications like renal involvement etc. Renal involvement included haematuria (>5 red blood cells/hpf) and proteinuria $\geq 2+$ by heat and acetic acid test or 24-hour urine protein >4mg/m²/hour and/ or blood pressure greater than 95th percentile for age and gender [8].

In the included patients, the data collected included age, gender, clinical presentations, and findings. Laboratory data including complete blood count, C-reactive protein, erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), complete urinalysis, and stool for occult blood. Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethics committee.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive statistics (frequency), Pearson chi square test and student t test. A P value of less than 0.05 was con-

sidered as statistically significant. Statistical package of social science software was used for statistical analysis.

Results

In this study, 65 patients were included. The mean age at presentation was 6.5 years (Range 2 to 12 years). There were 40 boys and 25 girls with a male preponderance (male to female ratio 1.6:1). The common presenting symptoms were purpuric rash (n=65,100 %) in all of the cases, followed by pain abdomen (n=42,64%), and arthritis (n=28,44%) (Table 1).

Other gastrointestinal manifestations like vomiting (n= 16,24%), Malena (n=3,5%) were present. Genitourinary symptoms like haematuria (n=3,4%), scrotal pain(n=4,6%), oedema (n=10, 15%), hypertension(n=20,30%) were seen. However none of them has oliguria or acute renal failure.

Table 1: Clinical profile

Clinical features	Frequency (n)	Percentage
Mean age range	2 to 12 years	
Male: female	1.6	
Purpuric rash	65	100
Pain abdomen	42	64
Vomiting	16	24
Arthritis	28	44
Hypertension	20	30
Malena	3	5
Scrotal pain and swelling	4	6
Subcutaneous oedema	10	15
Haematuria	3	4

*More than one finding was seen in all the children

Varying combinations of involvement of skin, joint, abdomen and the kidneys were seen during the disease course. When the laboratory parameters were assessed (Table 2), the mean platelet count was found to be 215,000 (240,000–540,000) L/mm³ and mean hemoglobin level was 7.2 (7.8–12 gm/dl). An elevated ESR (n=31,48%) and anaemia(n=33,50%) was present. Leucocytosis was

seen in 5 cases (18%), thrombocytosis in 13 (20%) patients with a mean platelet count of 2.65 L/mm³. ASO titre of >200 was found in 10 (15%) patients. Abnormal urine analysis was noticed in 10 (15%) patients, of which major abnormality was hematuria (n = 7, 7%). (Table 2). Rheumatoid factor was positive in 17(4%) also stool for occult was positive in 12(19%) cases.

Table 2: laboratory parameters

Lab parameter	Frequency (n)	Percentage
Anaemia	33	50
Leucocytosis	5	18
High ESR	31	48
Thrombocytosis	13	20
Stool for occult blood	12	19
ASO positive	10	15
Rheumatoid factor	17	4
Abnormal urinalysis	10	15
Abnormal renal function	7	10

Discussion

The mean age of onset of symptoms was 6.5 years with a male preponderance which is comparable to other studies [9-11]. In our study palpable purpura was seen in all the patients as seen in a study by Trapani et al, [13] purpura occurred in 100% of patients at some point during the course of the illness. Similar to our study, in previous studies rash was present predominantly in lower limbs and buttocks [16].

The classical gastrointestinal manifestations of HSP consist of nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, constipation, abdominal pain, malena. Gastrointestinal manifestations in a study by Abbas et al [9] and Krishnan et al [14] included abdominal pain in 56%, vomiting in 35% and melena in 19%. Comparable results to these were observed in our study with abdominal pain in 42(64%), vomiting in 16 (24%) and malena in 3(4%) none of them needed laparotomy.

Arthritis was seen in 44 of patients in our study with knee joint being most commonly affected. The incidence of arthritis in our study was lower than that in a study by Jauhola et al, [15] in which 90% of patients showed evidence of joint involvement.

Renal involvement is one of the dreaded manifestations in HSP. Renal involvement was defined as the presence of gross or microscopic haematuria with or without proteinuria. However, it was seen only in 5% of our patients and in most of the studies it ranged between 11% and 31% (27%) [17]

Various studies have reported scrotal involvement in HSP cases approximately in 10% of cases [18], in our study it was 6 %. Acute scrotal involvement might include scrotal rash and edema of scrotal soft tissue. It might be either unilateral or bilateral, and this pain mimics testicular torsion, though true torsion is rare. Our study didn't have any case of testicular torsion.

There is no specific diagnostic test for HSP. Anaemia was seen in 50% of patients, thrombocytosis in 20%, raised ESR 48% in a study by Abbas et al [19], anaemia was seen in 48%, raised ESR in 48% and thrombocytosis in 19% of patients quite comparable to our study. Stool occult blood was positive in 19% of patients, which was comparable to that in other studies

Conclusion

HSP appears to be quite common in the north part of our country with male preponderance in terms of involvement. Spontaneous recovery is seen with symptomatic management. The clinical profile of HSP in children was similar to that found in other studies except for renal involvement, which was much lower in this study. The occurrence of life-

threatening complications in HSP is very rare. There is a requirement for large scale prospective study to establish the standardized treatment protocol for HSP

References

1. Cassidy JT, Petty RE. Vasculitis. In: Text book of Pediatric Rheumatology, 3rd edn. Philadelphia, W.B. Saunders Company, 1995; pp 365-422.
2. Conn DL, Hunder GG, O'Duff JD. Vasculitis and related disorders. In: Text book of Rheumatology. Eds. Kelly WN, Harris ED Jr, Ruddy S, Sledge CB. Philadelphia, W.B. Saunders Company, 1993; pp 1077-1102.
3. Meadow SR, Glasgow EF, White RHR, Moncrieff MW, Cameron JS, Ogg CS. Schonlein-Henoch nephritis. Q J Med 1972; 41: 241-258.
4. Allen DM, Diamond LK, Howell DA. Anphylactoid purpura in children (Schonlein-Henoch syndrome): Review with follow up of renal complications. Am J Dis Child 1960; 99: 833-854.
5. Duvuru G, Stone JH. Henoch-Schönlein purpura. In: Imboden JB, Hellmann DB, Stone JH, editors. Current diagnosis and treatment. Rheumatology. 3rd ed. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill; 2013.
6. Trapani S, Micheli A, Grisolia F, Resti M, Chiappini E, Falcini F et al. Henoch Schonlein Purpura in childhood: epidemiological and clinical analysis of 150 cases over a 5-year period and review of literature. Semin Arthritis Rheum. 2005;35(3):143-53
7. Ozen S et al. The EULAR/PRINTO/PRES criteria for Henoch Schonlein purpura. Ann RheumDis.2010; 798-806
8. Paul Brogan and Aravind Bagga. Leucocytoclastic vasculitis. In: Ross E. Petty et al. editor. Textbook of Paediatric Rheumatology. 7th edition. Saunders Philadelphia. 2016; 452-459.
9. Abbas S, Geetha S, Deepthi RV, Kamar J, Uthup S. Clinical profile and outcome of Henoch Schonlein purpura in a tertiary care hospital in South India. Int J Contemp Pediatr 2017; 4:822-6.
10. Albaramki J. Henoch-Schonlein purpura in childhood a fifteen-year experience at a tertiary hospital. J Med Liban. 2016 JanMar;64(1):13-7
11. Lardhi AA Henoch-Schonlein purpura in children from the eastern province of Saudi Arabia Saudi Med J. 2012 Sep; 33(9):973-8.
12. Bagga A, Kabra SK, Srivastava RN, Bhunyan UN. Henoch Schonlein purpura in North Indian children. Indian Pediatrics 1991; 28:1153 - 1157.
13. Trapani S, Micheli A, Grisolia F, et al. Henoch Schonlein purpura in childhood: epi-

- demiological and clinical analysis of 150 cases over a 5-year period and review of literature. *Semin Arthritis Rheum* 2005; 35(3):143-53.
14. Krishnan DK, Padma BK. Clinical profile of Henoch-Schonlein purpura in children. *J. Evolution Med. Dent. Sci.* 2018; 7(22):2671-2673, DOI: 10.14260/jemds/2018/601
 15. Jauhola O, Ronkainen J, Koskimies O, et al. Clinical course of extrarenal symptoms of HSP: a 6 month prospective study. *Arch Dis Child* 2010;95(11):871-6
 16. Association CM. *Medicine - Guide of Clinical Diagnosis and Treatment*. Peking: People's Medical Publishing House; 2007.
 17. Shah G. Clinical profile and pattern of Henoch-Schönlein purpura in children. *J Patan AcadHealth Sci* 2015;2:17-21
 18. Chao NS, Wong BP, Leung MW, Chung KW, Kwok WK, Liu KK. Acute gastrointestinal and genito-urinary manifestations in children with HenochSchönlein purpura. *HK J Paediatr (NewSeries)* 2009; 14:168-71.
 19. Abbas S, Geetha S, Deepti RV, et al. Clinical profile and outcome of Henoch-Schonlein purpura in a tertiary care hospital in south India. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics* 2017; 4(3):822-6.